

1 **Solar photo-assisted electrochemical processes applied to actual**
2 **industrial and urban wastewaters: a practical approach based on**
3 **recent literature**

4 Authors: I. Salmerón^a, I. Oller^{a*}, S. Malato^a.

5 ^a*Plataforma Solar de Almería. Ctra Senés km 4, 04200 Tabernas (Almería), Spain.*

6 *Corresponding author: Dra. Isabel Oller (*isabel.oller@psa.es*)

7
8 **Abstract**

9 The application of electrochemical processes for wastewater treatment has increase
10 significantly in the last two decades. However, most of the works are focused on lab-
11 scale systems testing in saline simulated solutions spiked with a reference organic
12 compound, evidencing the scarcity of studies on actual wastewaters through a more
13 realistic practical approach. The aim of the present work is assessing the performance of
14 electrochemical treatments in actual matrices, considering the formation of different
15 oxidants species, apart from hydroxyl radicals, from dissolved ions contained in target
16 effluents as well as both, the regeneration of Fe²⁺ and their combination with a light
17 irradiation source. The degradation of a mix of microcontaminants in water matrices
18 with different complexity by solar photoelectron-Fenton at natural pH and at pilot scale
19 has been carried out at Plataforma Solar de Almería. Higher degradation rates were
20 obtained when focusing on the more complex and saline matrices. In addition, complex
21 industrial wastewaters mineralization was also studied by means of solar assisted
22 electro-oxidation, showing the crucial role of ammonium concentration in the effluent,

23 since it acts as a competitor for active chlorine species and so reducing the
24 mineralization rate.

25 **Keywords:** Actual wastewater, advanced oxidation processes, Electro-oxidation,
26 Fenton-like processes, Hydroxyl radicals.

27 **1. Introduction**

28 Nowadays society's lifestyle encourages a high rate of consumption of natural water
29 resources, meaning that an inadequate management will lead to a certain degree of
30 scarcity in the long term. Specifically, chemical industry undergone a strong
31 development owed to a growing demand for new products to satisfy the needs of the
32 consumers. The manufacture of drugs, personal care products or pesticides and
33 fertilizers to improve agricultural production, jointly with other organic substances
34 widely used in modern life, has led to the appearance of new water contaminants, either
35 at high concentrations (mg L^{-1}) in industrial wastewaters or at much lower
36 concentrations ($\text{ng-}\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) in urban wastewaters (known as micro-contaminants, MCs).
37 MCs effect on the environment is under study, but their toxicity and high persistence
38 have been widely demonstrated. They are difficult to assimilate for microorganisms
39 thus being accumulated and active in the environment for long periods of time and with
40 still unknown effects on the discharge ecosystems (Patel et al., 2019). That situation
41 motivates arisen, development and application of new highly oxidizing technologies
42 (Kanakaraju et al., 2018), aiming the degradation of these compounds of emerging
43 concern and even, depending to their organic load and complexity of the wastewater,
44 enhancing the biodegradability of the whole effluent.

45 In this context, electrochemical processes pose a versatile, useful and powerful tool for
46 the depuration of a wide variety of wastewaters, since only by applying an electric

47 current or electrode potential a broad spectrum of organics can be eliminated. They can
48 be applied as a tertiary treatment for the degradation of MCs as well as for the suitable
49 depuration of very complex industrial wastewaters with high toxic organic load and/or
50 low biodegradability, being applied as a pre-treatment until making the effluent enough
51 biocompatible (Urriaga et al., 2018; Mousset et al., 2020). In fact, electrochemical
52 processes pose an appropriate complement to other technologies such as membrane
53 systems, since the high ionic content of membrane rejections facilitates the flow of
54 electrons obtaining lower energy consumptions compared with other less saline
55 effluents (Pan et al., 2019; Soriano et al., 2020).

56 Some electrochemical processes have been widely used at industrial scale. For instance,
57 electrocoagulation implies an advantage over the conventional coagulation-flocculation
58 physicochemical process, since avoids the addition of chemical reagents by the use of
59 sacrificial electrodes, generating a lower amount of sludge, and presenting higher
60 efficiency in colloids removal (Barrera-Díaz et al., 2014) and even in pharmaceuticals
61 removal (Zaied et al., 2020). Despite involving great advantages such as an easy control
62 of the process and therefore easy automatization as well as the absence of external
63 reagents, other processes such as electrochemical oxidation, photoelectro-Fenton (PEF)
64 or photoelectrocatalysis have not been evaluated further than at laboratory scale and
65 very often by using model wastewaters.

66 Making an overview of the current literature (from year 2000 to nowadays), more than
67 7500 articles have been published on the use of electrochemical treatments for water
68 purification with a significant increase since 2012 (Fig.1). Most of these works are
69 mainly focused on the development of new materials for the manufacture of electrodes
70 and the effectiveness achieved in the degradation of a reference contaminant in a simple
71 water matrix. However, works addressing the application of these electrochemical

72 processes in actual water matrices are a few hundreds (Moreira et al., 2017). Therefore,
73 it is evident the scarcity of studies facing these technologies under a realistic approach
74 and for the purification of complex water matrices, which has limited the possibilities of
75 electro-oxidative systems from a commercial standpoint.

76

77 **Fig. 1.** Publications from Scopus DataBase focused on the study of electrochemical
78 processes since 2000 (revised on November 2020).

79 It is important to note that, from the inorganic ions naturally contained in waters, a large
80 amount and variety of oxidizing species can be generated, which entails an intrinsic
81 improvement over the basic studies in model waters using a supporting electrolyte
82 whose only function is to allow the transition of electrons. This was evidenced in
83 Garcia-Segura et al. (2018) where the efficiency of the electro-oxidative process as a
84 treatment for actual effluents from different sources was reported, revealing the
85 fundamental role of active chlorine species (ACS) for the degradation of organic matter.

86 Furthermore, some electrogenerated species are photoactive, which means that just by
87 irradiating the solution (usually with short wavelength light) the generation of different

88 oxidizing species could be promoted, which would result in an increase of the
89 contaminant degradation rate. This means that it is necessary to carry out an evaluation
90 of these electrochemical systems under actual conditions with real effluents as obtained
91 results may significantly diverge from those performed under model/simulated
92 conditions.

93 Few works are focused on covering the gap between small and large scale systems such
94 as the one published by Garcia-Rodriguez et al. (2020), which shows the possible
95 strategies to be followed depending on the type of water to be treated, emphasizing the
96 importance of process optimization and cost-efficiency. Furthermore, regarding photo-
97 electro-chemical processes, the study of Mousset and Dionysiou (2020) reviews the
98 possible configurations of electrochemical photo-reactors and the work of Brillas et al.
99 (2021) focuses on a more efficient use of light in this type of electro-chemical systems.

100 The present study deals with the application of solar-assisted electrochemical processes
101 on actual industrial and municipal wastewaters, discussing their performance as well as
102 their main mechanisms, especially focusing on persistent contaminants and MCs.

103 **2. Electro-oxidation processes**

104 Electro-oxidation can be addressed directly or indirectly. During direct electro-
105 oxidation, target contaminants are adsorbed on the anode surface where they are directly
106 oxidized by the transfer of electrons from the molecule to the anode avoiding the
107 intervention of any mediator. This treatment is possible as long as the applied potential
108 is low and keeps below the potential of oxygen evolution reaction, characteristic of the
109 specific material that conform the anode. Very often the process is governed by
110 adsorption so, as a consequence, degradation kinetics are low and strongly depend on
111 the anode electrocatalytic activity (Panizza, 2010). Moreover, another drawback of the

112 application of low potentials is evidenced by a decrease on the anode activity when time
113 of operation is increasing due to the formation of a layer of polymers from contaminants
114 or degradation by-products on the surface. This phenomenon is known as poisoning or
115 deactivation (Panizza, 2010). Likewise, polymers can be eliminated by the application
116 of a highly oxidative potential, thus regenerating the anode surface (Comninellis, 1994;
117 Panizza, 2010).

118 In indirect electro-oxidation, the oxidizing species are electrogenerated on the anode but
119 react in the bulk solution to oxidize organic compounds, so they can be considered as
120 the intermediaries transferring electrons between the anode and the organic
121 contaminants allowing the degradation of organics in the bulk solution, even far of the
122 anode surface. These oxidizing species can be generated from two sources, from the
123 intermediates generated as result of the oxygen evolution reactions (hydroxyl radicals,
124 •OH) or from the inorganic ionic species dissolved in water (chloride could produce
125 chlorine). The type and concentration of oxidant produced depends on the wastewater
126 composition but also on the width of the potential window of the electrode material. For
127 this reason non-active anodes, and specifically boron-doped diamond (BDD) anodes,
128 are able to generate different oxidants (Rychen et al., 2010), though in active anodes the
129 main oxidant generated is chlorine (Sáez et al., 2018).

130 2.1 Electrochlorination

131 One of the main inorganic ions that can be naturally found in waters is chloride. When a
132 contaminated water containing this ion undergoes an electrochemical depuration
133 process it follows two pathways: on the electrode surface via adsorbed chloro radicals
134 (reaction (1)) and by ACS (reactions (2 - 4)) (Panizza and Cerisola, 2009).

139 The solution pH determines the species of active chlorine that will be present in
140 wastewater. At pH below 7.55 (pKa), the main specie is HClO ($E^0 = 1.49$ V) and at
141 higher pH values, ClO^- ($E^0 = 0.86$ V) is predominant (reaction (4)). Despite the wide
142 use of these ACS for the degradation of organics, electrochemical and chemical
143 reactions occurring during the electro-oxidative process are partially unknown (Panizza
144 and Cerisola, 2009).

145 This electrochemically-assisted chlorine treatment, commonly known as
146 electrochlorination, presents several advantages regarding conventional chlorination
147 where ACS are added as a reagent (Martinez-Huitle and Brillas, 2009): (i) Transport
148 and storage of chlorine are not necessary, thus avoiding the risk associated; (ii) Organics
149 removal is faster than in chemical oxidation; (iii) Overall operation costs are lower.

150 As the treatment starts, ACS react with organic matter as soon as they are
151 electrogenerated so free available chlorine (FAC) concentration remains low, however
152 when the organic matter is completely eliminated, FAC begins to accumulate and so
153 oxidation process ends. When a BDD anode is used for the removal of organics in a
154 wastewater with high content on chloride, its high over-potential for oxygen evolution
155 leads in the generation of a huge amount of $\bullet\text{OH}$, thus promoting the oxidation of FAC
156 to undesired chlorine by-products (reactions (5 - 7)) (Bergmann, 2010; Groenen
157 Serrano, 2018). In such a case, the oxidative power of the process is reduced and water
158 toxicity increases entailing a serious risk for the ecosystems and human beings. To
159 avoid this effect, it is recommended to work at low potentials with BDD anodes so

160 diminishing the generation of ACS and $\bullet\text{OH}$ reducing the possible reaction between
161 both.

165 2.2. Electro-oxidation by other inorganic anions

166 When water purification is carried out by electro-cells with high oxygen evolution over-
167 potential anodes, organic contaminants are removed mainly by the oxidizing action of
168 electrogenerated $\bullet\text{OH}$. However, if the effluent to be treated is an actual wastewater
169 with sulphate, carbonate and phosphate ions, they can be oxidized on the anode surface
170 as described by reactions (8 - 10) (Cuerda-Correa et al., 2020):

174 The main advantage of these electrogenerated oxidants is that they are dissolved in the
175 aqueous solution, so that oxidative process extends beyond the areas adjacent to the
176 anode, thus avoiding the limitation of mass transfer on anode surface and increasing the
177 efficiency of the process (Panizza and Cerisola, 2009). In fact, at the beginning of the
178 treatment in which the concentration of organic pollutants is high, no significant
179 differences are found regarding the presence or absence of sulphate, carbonate and
180 phosphate ions. Nevertheless, when the concentration of organics is low and so the

181 system is limited in the adjacent area to the anode, the degradation process will be faster
 182 in wastewater with higher content of sulphate, carbonate or phosphate ions.

183 Farhat et al. (2017) evaluated the effect of this ionic species on the degradation process
 184 of 100 mg L⁻¹ of resorcinol by using different salt solutions whose main components
 185 were chloride, sulphate and nitrate. Different contaminant degradation rates were
 186 observed with only a single anion compared to a combination of them. Moreover,
 187 Ganiyu and Gamal El-Din (2020) studied the treatment of oil sand wastewater through
 188 electro-oxidation with BDD anodes, detecting the formation of radical and non-radical
 189 oxidant species, namely BDD([•]OH), SO₄^{•-}, CO₃^{•-}, S₂O₈²⁻, C₂O₆²⁻ and active chlorine.
 190 They confirmed their generation and their contribution in the overall organics
 191 degradation.

192 Considering the strong effect that these dissolved ionic species can have on a
 193 wastewater depuration by electro-oxidation, it is necessary to deepen on the application
 194 of electrochemical treatments to actual waters, whose natural compositions are highly
 195 variable. A summary of the main and most recent studies in which electro-oxidation has
 196 been applied for the depuration of actual industrial wastewaters is shown in Table 1.

197 **Table 1.** Main studies addressing application of electro-oxidation for the depuration of
 198 industrial wastewater effluents. COD: chemical oxygen demand.

Wastewater	Electrodes	Operating Conditions	Removal %	Reference
Herbicide wastewater	PbO ₂ anode - Ti cathode gap: 1 cm	<i>j</i> : 4 A dm ⁻² pH: 4 V: 1 L	87% of COD	(Zhang et al., 2020)
Sugar beet wastewater	BDD anode/Stainless steel cathode A= 109 cm ² gap: 1 cm	<i>j</i> : 49.1 mA cm ⁻² pH: 5 t: 294 min V: 1 L Adding NaCl	75% of COD	(Sharma and Simsek, 2020)

RO concentrate of petrochemical industry	Nb-BDD anode / stainless steel AISI 304L cathode A: 0.01 m ²	j: 20 mA cm ⁻² pH: 8 t: 5 h V: 1.5 L	71% of COD	(Wohlmut h da Silva et al., 2019)
RO concentrate of print and dyeing wastewater	PbO ₂ -Ti anode / Ti mesh-plate cathode. A: 300 cm ² gap: 1 cm	j: 10 mA cm ⁻² pH: 8.3 t: 40 min V: 1 L Q _{sp} : 2.45 Ah L ⁻¹	72% of COD	(Wang et al., 2018)
Washing machine effluent	Nb-BDD anode/Ti cathode A: 63.5 cm ²	j: 16.6 mA cm ⁻² t: 360 min V: 1 L	71% of COD	(Durán et al., 2018)
	Nb-BDD anode/Ti cathode A: 63.5 cm ⁻²	j: 66.6 mA cm ⁻² t: 180 min Adding 7 g L ⁻¹ of Na ₂ SO ₄	88.5% of COD	
Oxyfluorfen solution, raw (234 mg L ⁻¹) and ultrafiltration retentate	BDD anode / Stainless Steel AISI 304 cathode A: 78 cm ² gap: 9 mm	j: 500 mA cm ⁻² V: 0.6 L 590 kWh kg ⁻¹ Adding 1 g L ⁻¹ of Na ₂ SO ₄	50% of Oxyfluorfen raw solution	(Acosta-Santoyo et al., 2020)
Winery wastewater	BDD anode / Stainless Steel cathode A: 5 cm ²	j: 60 mA cm ⁻² t: 420 min V: 0.1 L	64% of COD	(Candia-Onfray et al., 2018)
Petroleum wastewater (Phenol)	28 Graphite anodes / 21 Stainless Steel cathodes A: 126 cm ² gap: 2 cm	j: 3.5 mA cm ⁻² pH: 7.5 - 9 t: 15 min V: 19.2 L E: 0.79 kWh m ⁻³	49-60 % of COD 100% Phenol	(Abou-Taleb et al., 2020)
Textile wastewater	2 Ti-RuO ₂ anodes / 2 Al cathodes A: 85 cm ² each gap: 1 cm	j: 1.66 A pH: 5.49 t: 80 min V: 1.5 L E: 0.68 Wh	80% of COD 97% color	(Kaur et al., 2017)
Methiocarb and Bisphenol A in sanitary landfill leachate	Si-BDD anode / Stainless Steel cathode A: 10 cm ² gap: 0.3 cm	j: 300 A m ⁻² pH: 8.5 t: 2 h V: 200 mL	>99% of Methiocarb and Bisphenol A	(Fernandes et al., 2020)

199

200 According to these studies, electro-oxidation is quite effective for the elimination of

201 organic compounds in complex waters, which would facilitate their subsequent

202 biological treatment or even safe disposal to the Environment. However, as both $\bullet\text{OH}$
203 and FAC would be present, the formation of chlorates and perchlorates in effluent
204 toxicity is an additional major challenge that must be tackled. This means that, at the
205 end of the treatment, it is necessary to evaluate the potential risks caused by these
206 chlorinated substances, in view of the potential end-use of the treated effluent.

207 2.3. Electro-oxidation combined with light irradiation

208 Many of electrogenerated species on the anode surface can be activated by different
209 methods, being the irradiation with light the most widely applied. New species with a
210 high oxidizing power could be generated, leading to an increase in the treatment
211 efficiency. This is the case of ACS which undergo photolysis when radiation is applied
212 generating active radicals as $\text{Cl}\bullet$ ($E^0 = 2.4 \text{ V}$) and $\bullet\text{OH}$ following reaction (11) in the
213 case of HClO and reactions (12) and (13) for ClO^- .

217 These reactions have been studied in detail mainly in the UV-C range at 254 nm of
218 wavelength (Feng et al., 2007). However, ACS photolysis could occur at other longer
219 wavelengths depending on the molar absorption, probably with lower quantum
220 efficiency (Fig. 2). In fact, ClO^- photolysis could take place even under solar radiation
221 since the molar absorption of ClO^- overlaps with UV-B and UV-A region of the solar
222 spectrum (from 280 to 400 nm) (Shu et al., 2014). This suggests that sunlight can be
223 applied in solutions containing ACS at pH higher than 7.5 aiming an enhancement in

224 the treatment oxidative capacity, which is known as solar-assisted anodic oxidation
225 (solar-assisted AO).

226

227 **Fig. 2.** Molar absorption of HClO and ClO⁻ vs solar irradiance spectrum at noon.

228

Modified from Shu et al 2014 (Shu et al., 2014).

229 On the other hand, S₂O₈²⁻, an alternative oxidant to H₂O₂ also widely studied, that can
230 be activated either by increasing temperature, by adding a transition metal catalyst or by
231 irradiating with light at 254 nm (reaction (14)), produces SO₄^{•-} (with a very high redox
232 potential E⁰ = 2.5 – 3.1 V, in the same range as [•]OH). For this reason, sulphate-based
233 treatments has been described in depth in literature for the removal of MCs and for
234 bacteria inactivation (Sánchez-Montes et al., 2020). However, mechanism involving
235 SO₄^{•-} generation and its role during electro-oxidative treatment is still under study.

237 Combination of an electrochemical treatment with a light source, whether artificial as a
238 lamp or natural as sunlight, leads to the promotion of electrogenerated oxidative species
239 to still more oxidizing ones. Therefore, efficiency of electrochemical processes could be

240 enhanced jointly with a reduction on the energy costs, which is one of the major
241 drawbacks of electro-oxidative treatments (Matzek and Carter, 2016; Dewil et al., 2017)

242 Despite the potential of these treatments, they have not yet been studied in depth with
243 actual wastewaters, with only a few studies in literature addressing the combination of
244 electro-oxidation with a light source. Sierra-Sanchez et al. (2020) studied a comparison
245 between the degradation of acetaminophen in a NaCl solution (2.5 g L^{-1}) by electro-
246 oxidation in the dark or illuminated with a UV-C lamp, obtaining higher degradation
247 rates under illumination. In Sanchez-Montes et al. (2020) it was also studied the
248 degradation of a model contaminant (glyphosate) in NaCl (2 g L^{-1}) by an electrochemical
249 cell illuminated with a UV-C lamp. However, that work addressed the behavior of the
250 system when using dimensionally stable anodes (DSA) or BDD, reporting a total
251 mineralization of glyphosate with DSA/UV-C but releasing chlorates. Luo et al. (2020)
252 studied the removal of four different bisphenol analogues but in this case, Na_2SO_4 was
253 used as supporting electrolyte, thus the formation of chlorate and perchlorates was
254 avoided. The results reported synergistic effects when combining UV-C and BDD,
255 increasing the degradation rate regarding UV-C and BDD stand-alone process and even
256 a toxicity reduction. One of the studies nearest to actual operating conditions was
257 published by Aravind et al. (2018), addressing the depuration of textile effluents. This
258 work confirmed the generation of oxychloride radicals by electron paramagnetic
259 analysis and evidenced the improvement entailed in the elimination of COD. In
260 addition, the light-assisted treatment resulted in lower amounts of chlorinated organic
261 compounds and in the absence of toxicity at the end of the treatment.

262

263

264 **3. Electro-Fenton and photo electro-Fenton processes.**

265 Electrochemistry is presented as a versatile tool for Fenton's reaction (reaction (15))
266 control. The combination of both is known as electro-Fenton (EF) process. In this
267 treatment, the anode generates oxidant species on its surface and simultaneously,
268 electrogeneration of H₂O₂ occurs by two-electron reduction of O₂ on the cathode
269 surface (reaction (16)), thus only with the addition of an iron salt, Fenton reaction is
270 promoted. Furthermore, Fe³⁺ obtained after Fenton reaction can be also reduced to Fe²⁺
271 on the cathode, regenerating the catalyst (reaction (17)) (Brillas et al., 2009; Sirés et al.,
272 2014) which is able to react again with electrogenerated H₂O₂, closing the cycle of the
273 catalytic process (Brillas, 2020). By means of the applied energy to the electrochemical
274 cell, the generation of oxidant species as well as Fenton reagents can be controlled,
275 allowing adapting the treatment according to the target wastewater characteristics.

279 The selection of the cathode material is of outmost relevance for H₂O₂
280 electrogeneration since it requires the use of specific and selective materials with a high
281 over-potential for H₂ evolution. Specifically, the most used materials are the carbon-
282 based, such as carbon-polytetrafluoroethylene (carbon-PTFE), carbon felt, reticulated
283 vitreous carbon or graphene, which are good electrical conductors, non-toxic, stable,
284 moderate cost and show a high over-potential for H₂ evolution with a low catalytic
285 activity for H₂O₂ reduction (Oturán and Oturán, 2018). To facilitate the cathodic
286 production of H₂O₂ it is convenient to have as much oxygen in solution as possible

287 thus, in filter-press cells, it is common to install an air chamber in the back side of the
288 cathode, working in a slightly higher pressure than water flow forcing the diffusion of
289 oxygen to the aqueous solution. These kinds of electrodes are known as Gas Diffusion
290 Electrodes (GDE).

291 EF process was the first technology considered as an electrochemical advanced
292 oxidation process (EAOP), presenting several advantages (Plakas and Karabelas, 2017):
293 (i) The in situ generation of reagent entails cost saving as well as avoid risks associated
294 to their transport and storage; (ii) The oxidation of contaminants can be easily
295 controlled by means of varying the current or potential applied; (iii) Easy automation
296 and monitoring of operating parameters.

297 EF can also be enhanced by the application of a light source, not only due to the
298 activation of electrogenerated species, but due to the regeneration of Fe²⁺ from Fe³⁺
299 generated during Fenton reaction (reaction (18)) ensuring the feasibility of the reaction.
300 This process is known as PEF when the irradiation source is a lamp and solar photo
301 electro-Fenton (SPEF) when it is developed under sunlight (Roccamante et al., 2019).

303 Nonetheless, most of the published studies address EF, PEF and SPEF process at
304 laboratory scale, with small systems treating low volumes of simulated wastewater,
305 focusing mainly on the development of new electrode materials. This evidences the lack
306 of studies carried out at larger scale and with complex water matrices, which would
307 serve as a preliminary step to the scale-up and future penetration of these systems into
308 the market. Among the most recent works treating actual wastewater with EF and SPEF
309 is the one developed by Mousset et al. (2018) in which 0.4 L of an electronic industry
310 effluent was treated by EF at pH 3, but adding 50 mM of K₂SO₄ in order to facilitate

311 the electrochemical process as well as reducing electrical energy consumption. In that
312 work, the removal of total organic carbon (TOC) achieved 94%. Salazar et al. (2019),
313 addressed the removal of Acid Blue 29 from an industrial textile wastewater by SPEF at
314 a pre-pilot scale and acidic pH by adding Na₂SO₄. After 6 h applying a current density
315 of 25 mA cm⁻² and a UV energy of 30 W m⁻², 93% of TOC was eliminated. Guelfi et al.
316 (2019) obtained similar results, removing 0.208 mM of bentazon spiked in an urban
317 wastewater effluent fortified with Na₂SO₄ with SPEF at pH 3.

318 Regarding the application of EF and SPEF in actual wastewaters at circumneutral pH, it
319 must be highlighted the new trend on studying the use of iron complexing agents to
320 maintain iron in solution as a new challenge for this technology. Only a few works have
321 already addressed this new approach (Ye et al., 2020; Salmerón et al., 2021).

322 **4. Addressing the challenge of solar electrochemical treatments applied** 323 **under actual operating conditions**

324 As mentioned in the previous sections, solar electrochemical studies conducted with
325 actual wastewaters are scarce, and if considering its combination with a light source, the
326 number of works published is even lower. This fact has hampered the development of
327 light-assisted electrochemical systems at pre-industrial level. Moreover, it would be
328 highly recommended to use, whenever possible, a renewable resource such as solar
329 energy as light source instead of artificial lamps.

330 In this context, Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA) has recently addressed the
331 application of electrochemical processes for the treatment of actual wastewaters,
332 assessing the possible improvements achieved by the combination of solar
333 photoreactors with an electrochemical pilot plant (Salmerón et al., 2019). The efficiency
334 of a SPEF pilot plant in the degradation of a mixture of two MCs, pentachlorophenol

335 (PCP) and terbutryn (TBT), contained in several aqueous matrices has been studied.
336 The first approach was the simplest one, 50 mM of Na₂SO₄ dissolved in distilled water,
337 then a highly saline simulated effluent and finally an actual highly saline wastewater.
338 The main objective was to verify the improvement in the performance of solar-assisted
339 electrochemical processes by treating actual wastewaters, with a great variety of ions
340 able to generate different radicals, when applying also a natural solar light source.

341 Complementarily, the treatment of two industrial effluents by means of a commercial
342 electrical cell assisted by solar energy was also studied in order to demonstrate that a
343 higher concentration of photo-active ions implies a higher performance of the system
344 and the requirement of lower electrical energy to achieve target treatment goals.

345 4.1 Materials and Analyses

346 PCP and TBT were selected as model compounds considering the list of priority MCs
347 reported in Directive 39/2013. Water matrices were spiked with a mixture stock solution
348 of PCP and TBT (from Sigma-Aldrich) at initial concentrations between 100 – 200 µg
349 L⁻¹. Fe³⁺:EDDS complex, (EDDS: Ethylenediamine-N,N'-disuccinic acid) in a
350 concentration rate of 0.1:0.2 mM, was prepared by adding Iron (III) sulfate x-hydrate
351 (~75% pure) from Panreac to acidified water (pH 2.8) and maintaining stirring and
352 darkness. After, the desired amount of EDDS (from Sigma-Aldrich) was added stirring
353 vigorously until the solution took a very intense yellow colour indicating the proper
354 formation of the complex.

355 Wastewaters treated in this work addressed from a saline solution to a highly actual
356 saline wastewater (Table 2), increasing gradually the water complexity to evaluate the
357 influence of the ionic content in the behavior of the oxidation system.

358

359 **Table 2.** Main characteristics of the wastewaters treated by electrochemical processes
 360 assisted by solar energy.

	50mM Na ₂ SO ₄	High salinity simulated effluent, HSSE	High salinity actual effluent, HSAE	Low salinity industrial wastewater, LSIW	High salinity industrial wastewater, HSIW
Conductivity (mS cm ⁻¹)	8.2	5.5 - 6	6.1 - 6.8	28	71
Turbidity (NTU)	-	-	9 - 45	308	N.A.
pH	6.2	8.7	8 - 8.6	7.4	7.2
DOC (mg L ⁻¹)	48	48	43 - 78	2040	2300
<i>Main ionic species</i>					
SO ₄ ⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	4800	1465	390 - 660	8245	29150
Cl ⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	-	555	1180 - 1960	4470	7930
NH ₄ ⁺ (mg L ⁻¹)	-	18	46 - 76	2670	9940

N.A. Non available; DOC Dissolved organic carbon.

361

362 MCs concentration was monitored by an UPLC/UV Agilent Series 1200 equipped with
 363 a ZORBAX Eclipse XDB-C18 analytical column. Analytical method consist on formic
 364 acid 25 mM in ultrapure water as eluent A and acetonitrile as eluent B. The gradient
 365 starting with 10% of eluent B, reaching 100% of B in 14 min at a flow rate of 1 mL min⁻¹
 366 ¹. Re-equilibration time was 3 min. Column temperature was 30° C and sample injection
 367 volume was 100 µL.

368 In the case of industrial wastewater, the efficiency of the treatment was assessed in
 369 terms of DOC elimination. This parameter was measured in a Total Organic Carbon
 370 Analyser TOC-V CSN from Shimadzu equipped with an ASI-V sampler after filtration
 371 through 0.45 µm nylon filter.

372 4.2 Experimental Setup

373 Ultraviolet radiation (UV) was measured with a CUV 5 UV radiometer from KIPP &
 374 ZONEN, located at PSA (Spain) and tilted 37° (the same as the CPC solar photo-

375 reactor), according to the latitude. Equation (19) provides the accumulative solar UV
376 energy applied in the treatment. This parameter allows comparison between different
377 solar processes (Malato et al., 2003).

$$378 \quad Q_{UV,n} = Q_{UV,n-1} + \Delta t_n \cdot \overline{UV}_{G,n} \cdot A_i / V_t; \quad \Delta t_n = t_n - t_{n-1} \quad (19)$$

379 $Q_{UV,n}$ (kJ L⁻¹) is the accumulated UV energy per unit of volume, $\overline{UV}_{G,n}$ (W m⁻²) is the
380 average solar ultraviolet radiation ($\lambda < 400$ nm) measured between t_n and t_{n-1} being n the
381 number of sample, A_i is the irradiated surface and V_t is the total volume.

382 The SPEF pilot plant installed at PSAis conformed by an electrochemical cell from
383 Electro-MP cells with a BDD anode on a niobium substrate and a carbon-PTFE GDE
384 cathode, both with an active area of 0.010 m². The cell is connected to a compound
385 parabolic collector (CPC) solar photo-reactor with 10 borosilicate glass tubes (4.5 cm
386 inner diameter) corresponding to 23 L of illuminated volume and 2 m² of irradiated
387 surface. Working conditions were established according to Salmerón et al. (2019) and
388 75 L of effluent was treated in each experiment.

389 Commercial DSA pilot plant comprised an electrochemical cell with five DSA anodes,
390 with a total active surface of 0.324 m², connected to a CPC solar photo-reactor with 24
391 borosilicate glass tubes (3.2 cm inner diameter) achieving an illuminated volume of 22
392 L and an illuminated area of 3.08 m². Operating conditions were established following
393 the manufacturer's recommendations and so applying a current density of 25 mA cm².
394 The maximum treatment capacity of the system per batch is 38 L.

395

396

397

398 4.2 Results and discussion

399 4.2.1 Solar photoelectron-Fenton pilot system

400 Experiments performed by adding 50 mM of Na₂SO₄ as supporting electrolyte, as well
401 as those with HSSE, were spiked with 200 µg L⁻¹ of PCP and TBT, respectively, while
402 HSAE were spiked with 100 µg L⁻¹ of each MCs, closer to actual wastewater
403 conditions. All SPEF tests were performed at natural pH, thus iron was maintained in
404 solution by using EDDS as complexing agent and so entailing an increase in DOC of 24
405 mg L⁻¹.

406 At the end of the treatment with 50 mM of Na₂SO₄, 80% MCs degradation was not
407 attained (Fig. 3a), after applying 6.5 kWh m⁻³ and a Q_{UV} of 10 kJ L⁻¹. In HSSE,
408 degradation was faster, requiring only 2.8 kWh m⁻³ and a Q_{UV} of 5.3 kJ L⁻¹ to achieve
409 80% of degradation of the sum of the MCs (PCP and TBT), even when the water had
410 lower conductivity (Table 2), the electric consumption was also lower. The main
411 difference was that HSSE contained more than 500 mg L⁻¹ chloride, thus not only •OH,
412 were generated at the anode but also the presence of ACS (reactions (1 - 4)), which, in
413 turn, could be activated by sunlight, increased significantly the oxidizing capacity of the
414 system. In fact, in Sanchez-Montes et al. (2020) it was reported the conversion of 76%
415 of HClO into radicals (reaction (11)) after 1 hour of treatment when irradiated with a 9
416 W UV-C lamp. In the case of sunlight, the irradiation available to interact with the ACS
417 is in the UV-A and UV-B range as shown in Fig. 2. Therefore, it is possible that the
418 conversion efficiency into radicals would be lower than with UV-C lamps, but with the
419 advantage of using a green and renewable energy source.

420 Regarding HSAE, the concentration of chlorides was higher than in HSSE, however it
421 contained higher organic matter background (43 – 78 mg L⁻¹ of DOC) which competed

422 with MCs for radicals and other oxidative species, slowing down the degradation
 423 process (Ferreira et al., 2020). As it is shown in Fig. 3b, at the end of the SPEF
 424 treatment of HSAE, 80% removal of the sum of MCs was not reached. Aiming to
 425 reduce the organics dissolved in the effluent, the treatment in HSAE was addressed by
 426 solar-assisted AO and thus the use of EDDS was avoided. Then, 80% of removal of
 427 MCs was attained after applying 2.6 kWh m⁻³ and 6.6 kJ L⁻¹ of accumulated UV energy.

428 (a)

429 (b)

430 **Fig. 3.** Degradation profile of the sum of both MCs (PCP and TBT) a) at 200 μg L⁻¹
 431 each dissolved in 50 mM of Na₂SO₄ and in HSSE treated by SPEF at pilot plant scale,

432 b) at $100 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ each in HSAE treated by SPEF and solar-assisted AO at pilot plant
433 scale.

434 *4.2.2 Dimensionally Stable Anodes pilot system*

435 On the other hand, non-biodegradable industrial effluents is one of the main depuration
436 challenges that must be faced by advanced technologies, not because the vast volume
437 produced but due to the high concentration of organic matter content (in the range of g
438 L^{-1} of DOC) which includes a huge amount of unknown hazardous and persistent
439 compounds. Electro-oxidation efficiency for mineralization of this highly complex
440 actual effluents is very low, however it can be improved when applying a light source,
441 as it was reported by (Alfonso-Muniozguren et al., 2020) for slaughterhouse
442 wastewater.

443 In the present study, the efficiency of DSA-based system assisted by solar energy was
444 evaluated for the treatment of a complex wastewater, showing the results in terms of
445 DOC and NH_4^+ removal. As shown in Fig. 4, the effectiveness of electrochemical
446 processes (solar-assisted AO) on mineralization is very low, being necessary a huge
447 amount of energy ($> 100 \text{ kWh m}^{-3}$ of electrical energy and $>100 \text{ kJ L}^{-1}$ of Q_{UV}) to
448 remove less than 50% of DOC. For this reason, instead of considering solar-assisted AO
449 as the unique treatment option, it could be applied as a pretreatment to improve
450 biodegradability enough in order to subsequently combine with a lower costly
451 biological treatment as it has been demonstrated in recent published studies (Ferreira et
452 al., 2020; Salmerón et al., 2020).

453 Furthermore, and contrary to what it could be expected, higher DOC degradation rate
454 was obtained in LSIW than in HSIW despite having a greater conductivity and a higher
455 chloride concentration. This can be explained by the very high concentration of NH_4^+ in

456 HSIW (9940 mg L⁻¹), which reacts rapidly with ACS thus reducing their availability to
457 oxidize organic matter (Wahman, 2018) or to generate radicals.

458 Therefore, application of electrooxidation processes should take into account the specific
459 characterization of target wastewater. As in DSA electrodes the main electrogenerated
460 oxidizing species are ACS, the effect of NH₄⁺ is even more detrimental in these systems
461 than in those with electrodes with a higher oxygen evolution over-potential and so able
462 to generate •OH, as BDD electrodes. This effect was also reported previously in Tirado
463 et al. (2018), where 95.2% of total nitrogen was abated with an RuO₂-based active
464 anode while 41.5% with BDD.

465

466 **Fig. 4.** DOC and NH₄⁺ removal in LSIW and HSIW (Table 2) by solar-assisted AO
467 with a DSA system.

468 5. Conclusions

469 The application of electrochemical treatments to actual wastewaters depuration poses an
470 enhancement on the oxidative power of the system, since available dissolved inorganic
471 ions could be precursors of different oxidative species. Research on electrochemical
472 processes must be upgraded to the treatment of actual wastewaters as

473 artificial/simulated saline solutions are far away of possible realistic industrial
474 applications. Furthermore, ammonium content in wastewaters is an essential parameter
475 to determine the efficiency of generated ACS by electrochemical processes.

476 Combination of an electrochemical system with a light source entails an enhancement
477 on degradation rates due to the generation of new oxidizing species, not only in classical
478 electrooxidation processes but also in electrochemical treatments based in Fenton,
479 Fenton-like and photo-Fenton where regeneration of Fe^{2+} is an important issue.

480 Considering the high electrical energy consumption (and related costs) that could imply
481 the application of electrochemical systems, a further challenge to be faced in the near
482 future is their combination with other technologies, either to supply the cells with a
483 renewable electrical energy source or to combine directly with solar irradiation.

484 **Acknowledgements**

485 The authors wish to thank the Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities
486 (MCIU), AEI and FEDER for funding this research under CalypSol Project (Reference:
487 RTI2018-097997-B-C32).

488 **References**

489 Abou-Taleb, E.M., Hellal, M.S., Kamal, K.H., 2020. Electro-oxidation of phenol in
490 petroleum wastewater using a novel pilot-scale electrochemical cell with graphite and
491 stainless-steel electrodes. *Water Environ. J. Performance of ultrafiltration as a pre-*
492 *concentration stage for the treatment of oxyfluorfen by electrochemical BDD oxidation.*
493 *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 237.

494 Alfonso-Muniozguren, P., Cotillas, S., Boaventura, R.A.R., Moreira, F.C., Lee, J.,
495 Vilar, V.J.P., 2020. Single and combined electrochemical oxidation driven processes for
496 the treatment of slaughterhouse wastewater. *J. Clean. Prod.* 270.

497 Aravind, P., Selvaraj, H., Ferro, S., Neelavannan, G.M., Sundaram, M., 2018. A one-pot
498 approach: Oxychloride radicals enhanced electrochemical oxidation for the treatment of
499 textile dye wastewater trailed by mixed salts recycling. *J. Clean. Prod.* 182, 246-258.

500 Barrera-Díaz, C., Cañizares, P., Fernández, F.J., Natividad, R., Rodrigo, M.A., 2014.
501 Electrochemical advanced oxidation processes: an overview of the current applications
502 to actual industrial effluents. *J. Mex. Chem. Soc.* 58, 256-275.

503 Bergmann, M.E.H., 2010. Drinking water disinfection by in-line electrolysis: Product
504 and inorganic by-product formation. in: Comninellis, C., Chen, G. (Eds.).
505 *Electrochemistry for the Environment*. Springer, pp. 163-204.

506 Brillas, E., 2020. A review on the photoelectro-Fenton process as efficient
507 electrochemical advanced oxidation for wastewater remediation. Treatment with UV
508 light, sunlight, and coupling with conventional and other photo-assisted advanced
509 technologies. *Chemosphere* 250, 126198.

510 Brillas, E., Serrà, A., Garcia-Segura, S., 2021. Biomimicry designs for
511 photoelectrochemical systems: Strategies to improve light delivery efficiency. *Curr.*
512 *Opin. Electrochem.* 26.

513 Brillas, E., Sirés, I., Oturan, M.A., 2009. Electro-Fenton process and related
514 electrochemical technologies based on Fenton's reaction chemistry. *Chem. Rev.* 109,
515 6570-6631.

516 Candia-Onfray, C., Espinoza, N., Sabino da Silva, E.B., Toledo-Neira, C., Espinoza,
517 L.C., Santander, R., Garcia, V., Salazar, R., 2018. Treatment of winery wastewater by
518 anodic oxidation using BDD electrode. *Chemosphere* 206, 709-717.

519 Comninellis, C., 1994. Electrocatalysis in the electrochemical conversion/combustion of
520 organic pollutants for waste water treatment. *Electrochim. Acta* 39, 1857-1862.

521 Cuerda-Correa, E.M., Alexandre-Franco, M.F., Fernández-González, C., 2020.
522 Advanced oxidation processes for the removal of antibiotics from water. An overview.
523 *Water* 12, 102.

524 Dewil, R., Mantzavinos, D., Poulios, I., Rodrigo, M.A., 2017. New perspectives for
525 advanced oxidation processes. *J. Environ. Manage.* 195, 93-99.

526 Durán, F.E., de Araújo, D.M., do Nascimento Brito, C., Santos, E.V., Ganiyu, S.O.,
527 Martínez-Huitle, C.A., 2018. Electrochemical technology for the treatment of real
528 washing machine effluent at pre-pilot plant scale by using active and non-active anodes.
529 *J. Electroanal. Chem.* 818, 216-222.

530 Farhat, A., Keller, J., Tait, S., Radjenovic, J., 2017. Assessment of the impact of
531 chloride on the formation of chlorinated by-products in the presence and absence of
532 electrochemically activated sulfate. *Chem. Eng. J.* 330, 1265-1271.

533 Feng, Y., Smith, D.W., Bolton, J.R., 2007. Photolysis of aqueous free chlorine species
534 (HOCl and OCl⁻) with 254 nm ultraviolet light. *J. Environ. Eng. Sci.* 6, 277-284.

535 Fernandes, A., Pereira, C., Koziol, V., Pacheco, M.J., Ciriaco, L., Lopes, A., 2020.
536 Emerging contaminants removal from effluents with complex matrices by
537 electrooxidation. *Sci. Total Environ.* 740, 140153.

538 Ferreira, L.C., Salmerón, I., Peres, J.A., Tavares, P.B., Lucas, M.S., Malato, S., 2020.
539 Advanced Oxidation Processes as sustainable technologies for the reduction of
540 elderberry agro-industrial water impact. *Water Resour. Ind.* 24, 100137.

541 Ganiyu, S.O., Gamal El-Din, M., 2020. Insight into in-situ radical and non-radical
542 oxidative degradation of organic compounds in complex real matrix during

543 electrooxidation with boron doped diamond electrode: A case study of oil sands process
544 water treatment. *Appl. Catal. B: Environ.* 279.

545 Garcia-Rodriguez, O., Mousset, E., Olvera-Vargas, H., Lefebvre, O., 2020.
546 Electrochemical treatment of highly concentrated wastewater: A review of experimental
547 and modeling approaches from lab- to full-scale. *Crit. Rev. Env. Sci. Technol.*, 1-70.

548 Garcia-Segura, S., Ocon, J.D., Chong, M.N., 2018. Electrochemical oxidation
549 remediation of real wastewater effluents—a review. *Process Saf. Environ. Prot.* 113, 48-
550 67.

551 Groenen Serrano, K., 2018. Indirect Electrochemical Oxidation Using Hydroxyl
552 Radical, Active Chlorine, and Peroxodisulfate. in: Martinez-Huitle, C.A., Rodrigo,
553 M.A., Scialdone, O. (Eds). *Electrochemical Water and Wastewater Treatment*, pp. 133-
554 164.

555 Guelfi, D.R.V., Brillas, E., Gozzi, F., Machulek, A., Jr., de Oliveira, S.C., Sires, I.,
556 2019. Influence of electrolysis conditions on the treatment of herbicide bentazon using
557 artificial UVA radiation and sunlight. Identification of oxidation products. *J. Environ.*
558 *Manage.* 231, 213-221.

559 Kanakaraju, D., Glass, B.D., Oelgemöller, M., 2018. Advanced oxidation process-
560 mediated removal of pharmaceuticals from water: a review. *J. Environ. Manage.* 219,
561 189-207.

562 Kaur, P., Kushwaha, J.P., Sangal, V.K., 2017. Evaluation and disposability study of
563 actual textile wastewater treatment by electro-oxidation method using Ti/RuO₂ anode.
564 *Process Saf. Environ. Prot.* 111, 13-22.

565 Luo, C., Hou, R., Chen, G., Liu, C., Zhou, L., Yuan, Y., 2020. UVC-assisted
566 electrochemical degradation of novel bisphenol analogues with boron-doped diamond

567 electrodes: kinetics, pathways and eco-toxicity removal. *Sci. Total Environ.* 711,
568 134539.

569 Malato, S., Blanco, J., Campos, A., Caceres, J., Guillard, C., Herrmann, J.M.,
570 Fernandez-Alba, A.R., 2003. Effect of operating parameters on the testing of new
571 industrial titania catalysts at solar pilot plant scale. *Appl. Catal. B: Environ.* 42, 349-
572 357.

573 Martinez-Huitle, C.A., Brillas, E., 2009. Decontamination of wastewaters containing
574 synthetic organic dyes by electrochemical methods: A general review. *Appl. Catal. B:*
575 *Environ.* 87, 105-145.

576 Matzek, L.W., Carter, K.E., 2016. Activated persulfate for organic chemical
577 degradation: a review. *Chemosphere* 151, 178-188.

578 Moreira, F.C., Boaventura, R.A.R., Brillas, E., Vilar, V.J.P., 2017. Electrochemical
579 advanced oxidation processes: a review on their application to synthetic and real
580 wastewaters. *Appl. Catal. B: Environ.* 202, 217-261.

581 Mousset, E., Dionysiou, D.D., 2020. Photoelectrochemical reactors for treatment of
582 water and wastewater: a review. *Environ. Chem. Lett.* 18, 1301-1318.

583 Mousset, E., Trelu, C., Olvera-Vargas, H., Pechaud, Y., Fourcade, F., Oturan, M.A.,
584 2020. Electrochemical technologies coupled with biological treatments. *Curr. Opin.*
585 *Electrochem.*, 100668.

586 Mousset, E., Wang, Z., Olvera-Vargas, H., Lefebvre, O., 2018. Advanced
587 electrocatalytic pre-treatment to improve the biodegradability of real wastewater from
588 the electronics industry—A detailed investigation study. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 360, 552-
589 559.

590 Oturan, N., Oturan, M.A., 2018. Electro-Fenton Process: Background, New
591 Developments, and Applications. in: Martinez-Huitle, C.A., Rodrigo, M.A., Scialdone,
592 O. (Eds). *Electrochemical Water and Wastewater Treatment*, pp. 193-221.

593 Pan, Z., Song, C., Li, L., Wang, H., Pan, Y., Wang, C., Li, J., Wang, T., Feng, X., 2019.
594 Membrane technology coupled with electrochemical advanced oxidation processes for
595 organic wastewater treatment: Recent advances and future prospects. *Chem. Eng. J.*
596 376, 120909.

597 Panizza, M., 2010. Importance of electrode material in the electrochemical treatment of
598 wastewater containing organic pollutants. in: Comninellis, C., Chen, G. (Eds.).
599 *Electrochemistry for the Environment*. Springer, pp. 25-54.

600 Panizza, M., Cerisola, G., 2009. Direct and mediated anodic oxidation of organic
601 pollutants. *Chem. Rev.* 109, 12, 6541–6569.

602 Patel, M., Kumar, R., Kishor, K., Mlsna, T., Pittman, C.U., Jr., Mohan, D., 2019.
603 Pharmaceuticals of Emerging Concern in Aquatic Systems: Chemistry, Occurrence,
604 Effects, and Removal Methods. *Chem. Rev.* 119, 3510-3673.

605 Plakas, K.V., Karabelas, A.J., 2017. Electro-Fenton applications in the water industry.
606 in: Zhou, M., Oturan, M.A., Sirés, I. (Eds.). *Electro-Fenton Process*. Springer, pp. 343-
607 378.

608 Roccamante, M., Salmerón, I., Ruiz, A., Oller, I., Malato, S., 2019. New approaches to
609 solar Advanced Oxidation Processes for elimination of priority substances based on
610 electrooxidation and ozonation at pilot plant scale. *Catal. Today.* 355, 844-850

611 Rychen, P., Provent, C., Pupunat, L., Hermant, N., 2010. Domestic and industrial water
612 disinfection using boron-doped diamond electrodes. in: Comninellis, C., Chen, G.
613 (Eds.). *Electrochemistry for the Environment*. Springer, pp. 143-161.

614 Sáez, C., Rodrigo, M.A., Fajardo, A.S., Martínez-Huitle, C.A., 2018. Indirect
615 Electrochemical Oxidation by Using Ozone, Hydrogen Peroxide, and Ferrate. in:
616 Martínez-Huitle, C.A., Rodrigo, M.A., Scialdone, O. (Eds). *Electrochemical Water and*
617 *Wastewater Treatment*, pp. 165-192.

618 Salazar, R., Gallardo-Arriaza, J., Vidal, J., Rivera-Vera, C., Toledo-Neira, C., Sandoval,
619 M.A., Cornejo-Ponce, L., Thiam, A., 2019. Treatment of industrial textile wastewater
620 by the solar photoelectro-Fenton process: Influence of solar radiation and applied
621 current. *Solar Energy* 190, 82-91.

622 Salmerón, I., Oller, I., Malato, S., 2020. Electro-oxidation process assisted by solar
623 energy for the treatment of wastewater with high salinity. *Sci. Total Environ.* 705.

624 Salmerón, I., Plakas, K.V., Sirés, I., Oller, I., Maldonado, M.I., Karabelas, A.J., Malato,
625 S., 2019. Optimization of electrocatalytic H₂O₂ production at pilot plant scale for solar-
626 assisted water treatment. *Appl. Catal. B: Environ.* 242, 327-336.

627 Salmerón, I., Rivas, G., Oller, I., Martínez-Piernas, A., Agüera, A., Malato, S., 2021.
628 Nanofiltration retentate treatment from urban wastewater secondary effluent by solar
629 electrochemical oxidation processes. *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 254, 117614.

630 Sanchez-Montes, I., Perez, J.F., Saez, C., Rodrigo, M.A., Canizares, P., Aquino, J.M.,
631 2020. Assessing the performance of electrochemical oxidation using DSA(R) and BDD
632 anodes in the presence of UVC light. *Chemosphere* 238, 124575.

633 Sánchez-Montes, I., Salmerón García, I., Rivas Ibañez, G., Aquino, J.M., Polo-López,
634 M.I., Malato, S., Oller, I., 2020. UVC-based advanced oxidation processes for
635 simultaneous removal of microcontaminants and pathogens from simulated municipal
636 wastewater at pilot plant scale. *Environ. Sci-Wat. Res.*

637 Sharma, S., Simsek, H., 2020. Sugar beet industry process wastewater treatment using
638 electrochemical methods and optimization of parameters using response surface
639 methodology. *Chemosphere* 238, 124669.

640 Shu, Z., Li, C., Belosevic, M., Bolton, J.R., El-Din, M.G., 2014. Application of a solar
641 UV/chlorine advanced oxidation process to oil sands process-affected water
642 remediation. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 48, 9692-9701.

643 Sierra-Sanchez, A.G., Linares-Hernandez, I., Martinez-Miranda, V., Almazan-Sanchez,
644 P.T., Teutli-Sequeira, E.A., Castaneda-Juarez, M., Esparza-Soto, M., 2020. Photo-
645 electrooxidation treatment of Acetaminophen in aqueous solution using BDD-Fe and
646 BDD-Cu systems. *Environ. Technol.*, 1-11.

647 Sirés, I., Brillas, E., Oturan, M.A., Rodrigo, M.A., Panizza, M., 2014. Electrochemical
648 advanced oxidation processes: today and tomorrow. A review. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. R.*
649 21, 8336-8367.

650 Soriano, A., Schaefer, C., Urriaga, A., 2020. Enhanced treatment of perfluoroalkyl acids
651 in groundwater by membrane separation and electrochemical oxidation. *Chemical*
652 *Engineering Journal Advances* 4, 100042.

653 Tirado, L., Gökkuş, Ö., Brillas, E., Sirés, I., 2018. Treatment of cheese whey
654 wastewater by combined electrochemical processes. *J. Appl. Electrochem.* 48, 1307-
655 1319.

656 Urriaga, A.M., Ibañez, R., Rivero, M.J., Ortiz, I., 2018. Integration of electrochemical
657 advanced oxidation with membrane separation and biodegradation. in: Martinez-Huitle,
658 C.A., Rodrigo, M.A., Scialdone, O. (Eds). *Electrochemical water and wastewater*
659 *treatment*. Elsevier, pp. 495-510.

660 Wahman, D.G., 2018. Web-Based Applications to Simulate Drinking Water Inorganic
661 Chloramine Chemistry. *J. Am. Water Works Assoc.* 110, E43-E61.

662 Wang, J., Zhang, T., Mei, Y., Pan, B., 2018. Treatment of reverse-osmosis concentrate
663 of printing and dyeing wastewater by electro-oxidation process with controlled
664 oxidation-reduction potential (ORP). *Chemosphere* 201, 621-626.

665 Wohlmuth da Silva, S., Venzke, C.D., Bitencourt Welter, J., Schneider, D.E., Zoppas
666 Ferreira, J., Siqueira Rodrigues, M.A., Moura Bernardes, A., 2019. Electrooxidation
667 Using Nb/BDD as Post-Treatment of a Reverse Osmosis Concentrate in the
668 Petrochemical Industry. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 16.

669 Ye, Z., Brillas, E., Centellas, F., Cabot, P.L., Sirés, I., 2020. Expanding the application
670 of photoelectro-Fenton treatment to urban wastewater using the Fe (III)-EDDS
671 complex. *Water Res.* 169, 115219.

672 Zaied, B.K., Rashid, M., Nasrullah, M., Zularisam, A.W., Pant, D., Singh, L., 2020. A
673 comprehensive review on contaminants removal from pharmaceutical wastewater by
674 electrocoagulation process. *Sci. Total Environ.*, 138095.

675 Zhang, L., Wei, F., Zhao, Q., Lv, S., Yao, Y., 2020. Real herbicide wastewater
676 treatment by combined means of electrocatalysis application and biological treatment.
677 *Chem. Ecol.* 36, 382-395.

678